

The ‘primates’ of Venetian Ithaca

A first sketch of the local administration with a list of *sindici*
(1649–1796)

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For Manti[†]

Under Venetian rule the island of Ithaca was ruled by a council of elders just as in ancient times, or so writes the Ithacesian author Karavias Grivas in 1849.¹ In his account of Venetian rule in Ithaca, the island’s old historian highlights the role of the local elders (*δημογέροντες*) and the tension with the governor of the island, elected from the Council of Cephalonia.² The

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Abbreviations: ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ = Γενικά Αρχεία του Κράτους–Τμήμα Ιθάκης; ΑΒΔ = Αρχείο βενετικής διοίκησης; ΓΑΚ–ΚΥ = Γενικά Αρχεία του Κράτους–Κεντρική Υπηρεσία. All dates are taken from the documents, old style (*stile vecchio*) unless otherwise indicated.

¹ ‘Η νήσος Ίθάκη ἐδιοικείτο, ὡς τὸ πάλαι, ὑπὸ μιᾶς δημογεροντίας Ἰθακησίων.’: Nikolaos Karavias Grivas, *Ἱστορία τῆς νήσου Ἰθάκης ἀπὸ τῶν ἀρχαιοτάτων χρόνων μέχρι τοῦ 1849* (Φ. Καραμπίνης και Κ. Βάφας, 1849), 69.

² The passage on Venetian rule at Karavias Grivas, *Ἱστορία τῆς νήσου Ἰθάκης*, 69–73. The treatment by Karavias Grivas is somewhat confused. After the fall of the Byzantine state into the hands of the Ottomans, he writes, the island came under the protection of the Venetians until 1797. The very fundamental confusion in this passage about the Ottoman presence may owe to the historian’s efforts to assimilate the history of Ithaca into general accounts of the modern history of mainland Greece, with which he was no doubt well acquainted as a learned reader (as shown by his collection of books catalogued at pp. ιδ’–κ’). The same motive probably explains the use of the term *δημογέροντες* and *δημογεροντία*, familiar from the old historiography, where the terms are used as Classicising titles for prominent Greek-speaking Christian subjects under Ottoman rule. Karavias Grivas published his work before the significant and more accurate study of Venetian government in the Ionian islands by Ermanno Lunzi, as Dimitris Prevezianos kindly pointed out to

elders of Ithaca strove for three centuries to liberate their island from the hands of outsiders, as Karavias Grivas would have it, speaking not of the Venetians but of the Cephalonians who were charged by the Venetians with ruling over their neighbours as subordinates.³ Though Karavias Grivas' *Ιστορία τῆς νήσου Ἰθάκης* (1849) stands out as an invaluable monument of the old historiography, we must be very cautious of his interpretation of the sources. Indeed his account of the role of Ithacians in the government of their island under Venetian rule does not quite line up with the evidence in the documents of the period, which provide the basis for this study. This article offers a first contribution towards understanding the unstudied system of local administration in Ithaca under Venetian rule (1500–1797), focussing on the highest officeholders elected among the Ithacan population, the *sindici* (σύνδικοι). While the existing scholarship has described the structure and function of the local administrations in most of the major Venetian possessions of the Greek-speaking world, little is said about Ithaca.⁴ By 'local administration', we mean the offices of government that were filled by local subjects rather than by colonial officials. In the case of the larger Venetian possessions, there is a clear contrast between offices

me: Ermanno Lunzi, *Della condizione politica delle Isole Jonie sotto il dominio Veneto* (Tipografia del Commercio, 1858). Still, Lunzi was reliant on Karavias Grivas's account and reproduced some of his errors, as I have mentioned in K. Nikias, 'The Governors of Venetian Ithaca', *Annual of the British School at Athens* 118 (2023): 405 n. 41. An interesting synthetic account of the role of local elites in the Greek-speaking territories in the Early Modern period in N.E. Karapidakis, 'Ἀρχοντες και αρχοντία 15ος-19ος αι.', *Τὰ Ἱστορικά* 30, no. 59 (2013): 282–324.

³ In particular, see the description of the petition of 1583 at Karavias Grivas, *Ιστορία τῆς νήσου Ἰθάκης*, 70–71. Cf. discussion of the error in Nikias, 'The Governors', 405 n. 41.

⁴ A useful survey, though without citations, in Aspasia Papadaki, 'Τοπικοί αξιωματούχοι και υπάλληλοι', in *Βενετοκρατούμενη Ελλάδα: Προσεγγίζοντας την ιστορία της*, ed. Chrysa A. Maltezos, vol. 1 (Ελληνικό Ινστιτούτο Βυζαντινών και Μεταβυζαντινών Σπουδών, 2010), 83–104. Note that the passage on Ithaca at p. 92 is clearly entirely derivative of Karavias Grivas, though not cited, and reproduces his inaccuracies. Some relevant comments also in Nikos P. Kapodistrias, 'Οι λύκοι που κατασπάραζαν τα πρόβατα: Η νομή της εξουσίας στην Ἰθάκη κατά την ὕστερη βενετική περίοδο (β' μισό 18ου αιώνα)', in *Πρακτικά του ΙΑ' Διεθνούς Πανιωνίου Συνεδρίου*, ed. Dora F. Markatou, vol. 5 (Εταιρεία Κεφαλληνιακών Ιστορικών Ερευνών, 2019), 655–57.

filled by Venetian patricians sent out from Venice to administer the colonies, and the lower-down offices filled by locals.⁵ Ithaca is a mixed case, because the higher offices were not filled by Venetians but by a Cephalonian elected annually to the post of governor. As the new evidence presented here shall show for the case of Ithaca, the arrangement of the lower offices in this small island's administration was formed in the image of the larger possessions but exhibits some curious particularities in need of study.

In this article, I make an attempt towards understanding this important 'local' aspect of government in Ithaca under Venetian rule in the light of unpublished documents from the state archive of Ithaca. The first part of this article outlines the rather complicated constitutional arrangements under which Ithaca was governed, and the history of this small apparatus of the Venetian state between the sixteenth and eighteenth centuries. The second part traces the role of the local administration with a focus on important reforms to the system which strengthened and expanded the role of Ithacians, reflecting the formalisation of an increasingly powerful local elite in the last decades of Venetian rule. The third part briefly surveys the various offices of the local administration, offering a framework for future work on the documents. In the Appendix are presented the names of the *sindici* of Ithaca between 1649 and 1796 as attested in the identified documents.

I. The structure of government in Venetian Ithaca

In the first decades after the Venetian capture of Ithaca together with Cephalonia in 1500 and its official resettlement in 1504 the governors of the island were sent from Venice.⁶ These early Venetian governors were presumably elected in the manner of other Venetian rectors sent to the colonies, though we have no evidence of their names or the organ from

⁵ See the definition in Papadaki, 'Τοπικοί αξιωματούχοι και υπάλληλοι', 83.

⁶ The outline in this section follows the presentation, with closer discussion of the primary sources, in Nikias, 'The Governors'. For simplicity, here I do not cite all the relevant sources and readers are directed to that article. Some further comments are found in K. Nikias, 'Σημειώσεις για τους διοικητές της Ιθάκης επί Βενετών', *Κεφαλονίτικη Πρόσδος* Γ', τ. 12 (2023): 34–38.

which they were elected. The few relevant sources tell us that this Venetian governor was aided by two Ithacesians who perhaps acted as counsellors in what must have been a small administrative setup. These arrangements came to an end, probably not coincidentally, in a period of regional turmoil marked by intensifying attacks by Ottoman forces on the Venetian possessions in the Ionian and culminating with the Ottoman-Venetian war of 1537–40.⁷ One figure of some prominence, Costa Puiese (or Konstantinos Pouliezos), showed himself useful by providing naval support to the Venetians at his own expense, a sacrifice for which he sought reward through the concession of the governorship of Ithaca. The petition of Costa Puiese was accepted by the Venetian Senate on 7 October 1536, awarding him with the right to govern the island for as long as he lived.⁸ The death of Costa sometime before 1563 was taken by the Cephalonian civic community (the body of citizens, or *cittadini*) as an occasion to request that the right to govern Ithaca be given to them. Their request was accepted, with the Cephalonian Council allowed to elect a governor of Ithaca each year, establishing the constitutional form of government over the small island which would survive until the end of Venetian rule in 1797. Still, after the death of Costa, the family Pouliezos kept a presence in Ithaca, his descendants enjoying some local prominence.⁹ A petition sent to Venice by Costa's grandson Pasqualin on 21 January 1574 refers to the premature death of his father in battle against the Turks and asks that he be allowed to take up the remaining four years in his father's term as governor (plus another two to allow him to marry off his sisters). While the family

⁷ Generally on the sixteenth century in Ithaca see D.P. Prevezianos, 'Ψάχνοντας για την Ιθάκη στις απαρχές της βενετικής κυριαρχίας: 1500–1600' [REGESTA ITHACAE HISTORIAE, II], *Bulletin of the Ithacan Historical Society* 1 (2023): 92–126.

⁸ Archivio di Stato di Venezia, Senato, Mar, Deliberazioni, reg. 23, ff. 183v–184r. See my earlier comments based on the citation of this document by Sathas, before discovering it in the register of the Senate, in Nikias, 'The Governors', Supplementary Material, s.v. Costa Puiese.

⁹ See some relevant sources cited in K Nikias, 'Private legal practice and public authority in early Venetian Ithaca: thirteen new notarial documents (1575–1599)', *Tijdschrift voor Rechtsgeschiedenis / Revue d'histoire du droit / The Legal History Review* 92, no. 1–2 (2024): 108 nn. 42, 115 nn. 69–70.

Pouliezos possibly had Cephalonian roots, with the name attested in Paliki in the early sixteenth century, this branch of the family was established in Ithaca and remained there.¹⁰ Documents from a legal dispute in 1686 show that this old Ithacan branch of the Pouliezos recalled its descent from the governor Costa and asserted their right to the privilege of being exempt from compulsory public service (*angaria*).¹¹ The Pouliezos provided at least two governors, perhaps three, dominating the government of the island in the mid-sixteenth century. If we are to consider them as established settlers in Ithaca, they represent an example of the participation of the local population in government of their island under Venetian rule.

This important experience of self-government by a kind of elite of the island's own was extinguished by the time of the regular election of governors by the Cephalonian Council, which sent one of its most prominent members to rule its neighbouring subjurisdiction for a term of one year. The posting was well sought-after, not merely as a source of prestige but an opportunity for enrichment. We can assume that regular elections for the governorship were well established by 1583, when the Ithacesians complain to Venice about the maladministration of their island by the Cephalonians sent as governors. The Ithacan petition recalls the

¹⁰ In a register of landholdings made in 1508 (*Descrittione possessionum Insule Cephallenie*), see the entry for 'una altra conzesion obtenuta dal magnifico miser Piero Foschollo soto di 23 zugno 1508, per la qual li conciede canpi de fituo de Thomo Pulexo, postti a Palichi de mozade 8 grande': Georgios S. Ploumidis, *Οι βενετοκρατούμενες ελληνικές χώρες: μεταξύ του δευτέρου και του τρίτου τουρκοβενετικού πολέμου, (1503–1537)* (Πανεπιστήμιον Ιωαννίνων, 1974), 133. Also Stamatoula Zapanti, *Κεφαλονιά 1500–1571, η συγκρότηση της κοινωνίας του νησιού* (University Studio Press, 1999), 171.

¹¹ In a petition presented by Stati Puglieso of 10 March 1686, 'La famiglia benemerita di Pugliesso venuta anticamente ad'Habitare in quest'Isola del Thiachi cio é due fratelli furono gratiati dalla Serenità del Prencipe di godere il Capitaniato di questa Isola, come il tutto viene Comprobato dalla annesse publiche scritture...': ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, «Σπαράγματα», Box 38, Fragments attributable to Francesco Cologna (1686), *Scritture instando*, f. 1005/1022/27r. The attachments include copies of earlier disputes raised by the family (apparently as early as 1593) that the descendants of Costa and his brother had been burdened with service in the *guardia* in contravention of their privilege of exemption from *angarie*. The petition and its attachments are cited briefly in Nikias, 'Private legal practice and public authority in early Venetian Ithaca', 108 nn. 42, 115 nn. 69–70.

early decades of that century, when their island was entrusted to a governor sent from Venice, who ruled alongside two local aides. Their request to have this old constitutional form restored is knocked back, with the Venetian Inquisitors Gritti and Garzoni insisting that it was sufficient for the Venetians to send a representative once per year for a month to supervise the administration and attend to matters too serious to delegate to the Cephalonian governor.¹² The crystallisation of the constitutional structure locked out the Ithacesians from the direct government of the island for the remaining two centuries of Venetian rule. However, there was a much more limited opportunity for the participation of Ithacesians in government through a number of local offices which exercised a range of functions. Evidence for these ‘civic offices’ (*uffici urbani* or *cariche urbane*) is presented in this article, for the first time offering an insight into the participation of local Ithacesians in the government of their island and the experience of power in the small island’s towns. As we shall see, not all the offices represent a privileged position reflecting the influence of the officeholder. Indeed, and extraordinarily by comparison with the arrangements in other Venetian colonies, the appointees to the lowest of the Ithacan offices were obliged to fill these roles as compulsory service to the state (*angaria*), a burden from which a handful of families enjoyed an exemption. We shall return to this evidence later.

The legal status of the Ithacan administration can itself be somewhat opaque in the sources. The constitutional structure of Venetian rule in Ithaca had the following form:

<i>Provveditor di Cefalonia</i>	
<i>Consiglier e vice gerente in visita del Teachi</i>	} Venetian patricians
<i>Governator e capitano del Teachi</i>	
<i>Consiglier e vice governator</i>	} Cephalonian <i>cittadini</i>
Other functionaries of chancellery	
<i>Sindici di Vati, Anoi, Oxoi</i>	} Ithacesians
and other <i>cariche urbane</i>	

¹² ‘basta la provvisione fatta che ogni anno vada un Clarissimo Consigliere alla Visita di detta Isola’: Nikias, ‘The Governors’, 404–5 n. 41.

While formally a subjurisdiction of the *reggimento* at Cephalonia, with its governorship conceded by right to the Cephalonian Community, the status of Ithaca in the hierarchy of Venetian government is sometimes blurred, even by the colonial administrators themselves.¹³ The island was administered by a small chancellery (*cancellaria*) based in a ‘public palace’ (*palazzo pubblico*) at the main township of Vathy (*Vati*), headed by the governor sent from Cephalonia and a counsellor (*consiglier*) whom the governor had the right to select and who sometimes deputised in his absence.¹⁴ There is some evidence that the chancellery was also staffed by a scribe (*scrivano*), and perhaps other functionaries, including an archivist (*pubblico archivista*) at least in the eighteenth century.¹⁵ In substance the chancellery operated in the image of a little *reggimento*, although formally it was merely an outpost of the administration at Cephalonia and subordinated to it in the constitutional hierarchy. The chancellery adopted documentary practices following the model of the larger Venetian administrations, the governor’s records adopting the forms used by the Venetian rectors.¹⁶

II. The local administration

The small Ithacan chancellery exercising the powers delegated to a governor elected by the Cephalonian council was subjected to the regular supervision of the Venetian government based at Cephalonia (*reggimento di Cefalonia*). In practice this was entrusted to one of the counsellors to the *provveditor*, who would represent the Venetian state during an annual visit of a month, usually taking place each March. Already by the late sixteenth century, the *provveditori* report back to Venice that their counsellors took

¹³ Some discussion of this in K Nikias, ‘Μία επισκόπηση του Αρχείου της Βενετικής Διοίκησης της Ιθάκης (1638–1797)’, in *Πρακτικά του ΙΒ΄ Πανιωνίου Συνεδρίου, Ζάκυνθος 18–21 Οκτωβρίου 2023*, (forthcoming).

¹⁴ Nikias, ‘The Governors’, 405 n. 43. On the governor’s ‘palace’ see K Nikias, ‘The Venetian Governor’s Palace on Ithaca’, *Mediterranean Studies* 32, no. 2 (2024): 156–81.

¹⁵ Nikias, ‘The Governors’, 405; Kyriaco Nikias, ‘The archive of the Venetian administration at Ithaca’, *Mediterranean Historical Review* 39, no. 1 (2024): 74–75.

¹⁶ Nikias, ‘The archive’; Nikias, ‘Μία επισκόπηση’.

the opportunity of their visits to this isolated corner of the jurisdiction to make a private profit, giving us cause to doubt the efficacy of the visits as a supervisory mechanism.¹⁷ The proper intention of the visits was for the Venetian counsellor to represent the *provveditor* on Ithaca by exercising certain powers reserved by the *reggimento* and not delegated to the governor. Possibly the most significant task undertaken by the counsellor was the appointment of selected Ithacesian subjects to a number of local civic offices (called *urbani officii* or *cariche urbane*).¹⁸ The process is formally described in the documents as an ‘election’ (*elezione*) but there was no ballot or deliberative participation of the ‘electees’, whom we had better consider appointees. These ‘elections’ were recorded in organised lists of offices and the names of the men appointed to them. The lists are preceded by a preamble of regular and formulaic type, with changes to the standard text reflecting reforms to the procedure for election over time. The standard preamble of the eighteenth century describes the establishment of the local offices ‘for the good government of these subjects’.¹⁹ The general mode of election was clearly established by the time of the first surviving list in 1655 (see Figure 1), but key reforms were made in 1683, 1781, and probably again in the last decade of Venetian rule, as we shall see. The original lists were recorded by the visiting counsellor and taken to Cephalonia, though none have been identified among the Venetian administrative documents

¹⁷ Nikias, ‘The Governors’, 404. On evidence that the frequency of the visits was reduced to two years in 1726, and to four years in 1781, see my comments below at n. 27.

¹⁸ The hitherto discovered lists of electees are cited together with the extracted names of the elected *sindici* in the Appendix.

¹⁹ For example, from 1753: ‘L’Illustrissimo, et Eccellentissimo Signor Andrea Venier Consigliere e Vice Gerente in questa Visita del Thiachi sedendo, per devenire all’elezione dell’infrascritte cariche et officii stabiliti per il buon governo di questi suditi avuta sotto l’occhio la nomina fatta dalli Sindici, e Primati delle Ville colle necessarie informazioni dell’Spetabile Signor Governatore e Capitano giusto al prescritto delle Terminazioni dell’Eccellentissimo Signor Giacomo Cornèr fù Provveditor General dà Màr a norma dela quali hà eletto ut infra’: ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, vol. Μ. Μεταχά (1753), *Libro primo straordinario*, ff. 112r–113v (31 March 1753). The other preambles follow the same model, with variations to this text usually made when reforms were decreed to the system of election, as described in this article.

held at the Archive of Cephalonia, which has suffered great losses.²⁰ Fortunately, official copies of the lists were made into the documents of the governor in Ithaca which are held in the ‘Archive of the Venetian administration’ at the local Archive.²¹ These are invariably recorded into the *Libro Estrordinario* or *Libro Diversorum* (registers kept by the chancellery containing acts of miscellaneous type) and apparently copied on the same day as the election, most often bearing the original signature of the visiting counsellor on the copy (see Figure 2). Beyond their significance for an insight into the local experience of government in Ithaca, the election documents also allow us to reconstruct the names of the Venetian counsellors of the *provveditor* in Cephalonia.

The procedure followed by the visiting counsellors to elect the officeholders can only be reconstructed along vague lines. Until 1683 the preambles to the lists of election state that appointees were nominated by the governor to the visiting counsellor (formulaically, *prese le debite informazioni dal spettabil signor Governator e Capitano*), leaving unclear whether the Ithacesians had any role.²² A large number of reforms to legal and administrative practices in Ithaca is issued by the *provveditor general da mar* Giacomo Corner in 1683 in a ‘Settlement between Cephalonia and Ithaca’ (*Sentenza trà Citta di Cefalonia e Tiachi*).²³ The reforms establish a

²⁰ I have benefited from discussions about this with Dr Despina Vlasi. A description of the Venetian fonds at Cephalonia in Theodora Zafeiratou, ‘The General State Archives of Cephalonia and the Venetian Archives of the Island’, in *Alimentazione, cibo e gastronomia nello Stato da mar e altri contributi, Atti dell’VIII convegno internazionale Venezia e il suo Stato da mar, Venezia, 13–15 febbraio 2020*, ed. Bruno Crevato-Selvaggi (Società Dalmata di Storia Patria, 2022), 85–94.

²¹ ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ: Αρχείο βενετικής διοίκησης (unclassified), here cited passim ΑΒΔ. On the archive see Nikias, ‘The archive’.

²² E.g. ‘L’Illustrissimo Signor Vincenzo Donado Consigliere e Vice Gerente sedendo per divenire all’ electione delli infrascritti officii con l’informazine e assistenza del Spettabil Signor Governator e Capitano di quest’ Isola, Ha eletto e creato come segue.’: ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, vol. Francesco Cologna (1673–75, i) f. 76v (29 March 1675).

²³ ΓΑΚ–ΚΥ, ms. 229, f. 81r–82r (*Sentenza trà Citta di Cefalonia e Tiachi*, issued by Giacomo Corner Cavalier *provveditor general da mar* on 2 December 1683). This copy gives Corner’s name as ‘Gerolamo’, clearly an error, given the proper name of the *provveditor general da mar*, Giacomo, is correctly given in citations to the reforms in other

requirement for the involvement of the *sindici* in this process, being the highest ranking of the officeholders.²⁴ The *sindici* were invariably prominent local figures in their communities and acted as informants to the administration by providing a nomination to guide the counsellor's choice of candidates to fill the remaining offices. These were the *provveditori alla sanità, giustizieri, deputati alle strade, deputati all'estime, contestabili, and cartofori*. After 1683, the preamble to the lists is altered to include express reference to the Corner reforms, and in several later examples this further specifies the involvement of the *sindici*.²⁵ The reforms of 1683 were made in response to a petition by the Ithacesians, to which the orders respond by offering regulatory solutions to the cause of the dispute with the Cephalonians. These were just one in a series of many appeals by the Ithacesians to the Venetian authorities for relief from their Cephalonian governor, with petitions being sent in complaint already in the late sixteenth century soon after the concession of the governorship to the Cephalonians.²⁶

Further significant reforms were issued in 1781 by the *provveditor general da mar* Giacomo Gradenigo, again in response to the petition of the Ithacesians the year before.²⁷ The surviving lists from the annual

legal instruments, as in orders of the *provveditor general da mar* Agostin Sagredo in 1753: Despina Vlassi, 'Το Συμβούλιο των 150 της Κεφαλονιάς. Τα πρώτα αβέβαια βήματα ενός θεσμού χωρίς μέλλον', in *Τόμος αφιερωμένος στον ακαδημαϊκό δάσκαλο Κωνσταντίνο Ντόκο*, ed. Vaios Vaiopoulos, Stathis Birtachas, and Gerasimos Pagratis (Ηρόδοτος, 2021), 183. Note in an earlier work where I cite these orders I gave the incorrect name, as it appears in this copy: Nikias, 'The Governors', 406.

²⁴ See the decision in response to petition item XV: 'Nel Decimo quinto, termina che intutte l'ellectioni di quegl'Offizj, e Cariche debbano quei Sindici attuali, e Vecchiardi dell'Isola nominar alla presenza del Governator, e Capitano le Persone, che fossero per promonersi all'impiego di dette Cariche, et Offizj, come pure nell'ellectione de' Sindici medesimi, debbano con la preddetta norma far la nomina, acciò di tal numero siano dall'Illustrissimo Consiglier trasciolti i trè più abili, e così pure dallo stesso provvedutte con la medesima prattica l'altre Cariche, et Offizj, altrimenti ogni ellectione fatta in forma diversa sij nulla, e con pena ad'arbitrio.': *ibid*, f. 81v.

²⁵ Cf. above n. 19.

²⁶ Several examples are discussed in Nikias, 'The Governors'.

²⁷ ΓΑΚ-ΚΥ, ms. 229, ff. 148v-149v (hereafter *Ordini Gradenigo*). Article I of the orders of Gradenigo concerns another significant reform, namely concerning the frequency of

elections after this date cite the Gradenigo reforms in their preamble.²⁸ The reforms set the number of elected *sindici* to two from Vathy, and one from each of Anogi and Exogi, who together would be known as the *Sindici dell'Università dell'Isola*.²⁹ Each year upon the assumption of rule by the new governor, the *sindici* were to be obliged to provide to him with a list of names of candidates for the other offices, among whom the governor was to select the most suitable.³⁰ The election would then be effected by a formal order of the governor, handed to the archivist, and registered in a book kept by the community (*università*).³¹ The election may have been witnessed one year by André Grasset de Saint-Sauveur, the French consul general at Zante in the 1780s, whose travel memoirs record how the 'primates [i.e. *sindici e primati*] of Ithaca assemble each year, under the supervision of the governor, in a church, and they nominate the municipal offices.'³²

the visits to the island by the Venetian counsellors: at f. 148v. While the supervisory visits were established by the late sixteenth century as an annual event, the orders of 1781 refer to a petition of the Ithacesians to reduce the frequency from each two years to each four years. The reduction from annual to biannual visits appears to have been established with *ducali* of 22 June 1726, which are cited by Gradenigo. These reforms to the important supervisory mechanism of the visit must remain for closer study. Rather interestingly, Karavias Grivas sketches the reforms to the frequency of the visit more or less correctly with a broad stroke: Karavias Grivas, *Ιστορία τῆς νήσου Ἰθάκης*, 72.

²⁸ The election of 1784: ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, «Σπαράγματα», Box 18, Fragments of Zuanne Anino, f. [144]r. The election of 1787: ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, «Σπαράγματα», Box 24, Fragments attributable to Teodoro Assani, [*Libro straordinario?*], f. 7r (Vathy), f. 9r (Anogi), f. 14r (Exogi).

²⁹ *Ordini Gradenigo* (above n. 27), f. 149r.

³⁰ *Ordini Gradenigo* (above n. 27), f. 149r.

³¹ 'La nomina medesima dovrà essere fermata dai proponenti Sindici, nè oltre i Nomi in quella contenuti potrà cadere la scielta, la quale verà tantosto estesa in Libro con positivo Decreto di quel Spettabile Governator, e ne sarà tosto data legal copia autentica gratis da quel Ministro Cancelliere ai Vecchi Sindici, per esser passata in mano del loro Archivista, e registrata nel Libro tenuto da quella Università': *Ordini Gradenigo* (above n. 27), f. 149r.

³² 'Les primats de Thiaqui s'assembloient chaque année, sous l'inspection du gouverneur, dans une église, et ils nommoient aux charges municipales.': André Grasset de Saint-Sauveur, *Voyage historique, littéraire et pittoresque dans les isles et possessions ci-devant vénitiennes du Levant*, vol. 3 (Tavernier, 1800), 9. Saint-Saveur's contact with Ithaca is incidentally attested by several letters he sent regarding the currant trade, which are

At their face value, the reforms of 1781 appear to have a merely formal significance. They increased the power of the Cephalonian *cittadino* holding the office of governor at the expense of his superior in the Venetian counsellor. Formally speaking, this shift therefore decreased the scope of the ‘reserved’ powers of the *reggimento* and increased those conceded to the governor. In substance, however, this reform was of more consequence for the local administration in Ithaca. The limiting of the numbers of the *sindici* of the three towns, together with the restatement of their right to a role in the election of their peers to lower offices, represents a strengthening and formalisation of the powers of an emerging Ithacesian elite. Further reforms after 1781, which we can only reconstruct from scattered indications across different documents, moved in the same direction, expanding the role of Ithacesians themselves in the election of the local officeholders. The most significant of these reforms to the constitutional structure of Venetian government in Ithaca was the establishment of a deliberative body, either a council (*consiglio*) or *conclave*, constituted by Ithacesians. Until this point, there was no deliberative body in Ithaca, which was formally speaking a subjurisdiction of neighbouring Cephalonia with its governor elected by the council of the larger island.³³ From an account of Venetian government written by a later administrator in 1805, the establishment of a deliberative body in Ithaca is attributed to reforms issued by the *provveditor general da mar* Nicolò Erizzo who served during the period 1784–86.³⁴ The old historian Karavias Grivas writes that an

preserved in ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, «Σπαράγματα», Box 36, Fragments attributable to Spiridion Loverdo, [*Filze lettere*], Letter of 20 December 1782 (in French with attached Italian translation), and another letter of 22 December 1782. Also ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, «Σπαράγματα», Box 5, Fragments attributable to Andrea Anino (1742), [*Filze lettere*], among which a misplaced letter of Saint-Saveur dated 13 March 1784, lodged between ff. 374 and 375. This letter is addressed ‘A Messieurs Les Sindics et Notables de l’isle de Thiaqui’.

³³ Nikias, ‘The Governors’. On the operation of the Council of Cephalonia and its reform, there are several extensive studies by Vlasi, most recently: Vlasi, ‘Το Συμβούλιο των 150’.

³⁴ See Gerasimos Livitsanis, ‘Το «Δίμπρο ντ’ Όρο» της Ιθάκης του έτους 1799: Μια πρώτη παρουσίαση’, *Bulletin of the Ithacan Historical Society* 2 (2024): 191–234. Thanks are due to Gerasimos Livitsanis for having shared this important discovery with me before its publication. A list of *provveditori generali da mar* is usefully provided in Christina E

order of 1787 saw elections of the local offices put to a vote, by which he probably alludes to the establishment of a council or *conclave*.³⁵ Despite my efforts to trace records of the council among the surviving Venetian documents at Ithaca, I have only been able to locate a handful of mentions of a *Consiglio di Teachi* (1791) and a *Conclave* (1794).³⁶ We are limited by the state of the documents of the last two decades of Venetian rule, which is rather poor by comparison to earlier documents in the series.³⁷ While we must leave the important subject of the establishment of a deliberative body in Ithaca for further, more intensive study, it is relevant for our purposes that both the identified references to such an institution concern disputes over its role in the elections of *sindici*. The first series of documents concerns a dispute raised by Antonio Draculi (son of the late Spiro) in 1791 against the procedure taken by the *Consiglio di Teachi* in removing him as the elected *sindico* and replacing him with Spiro Caravia (son of the late Costantin).³⁸ The second is not dissimilar, concerning a dispute raised by Basilio Galati (son of the late Zaneto) against the election by the *Conclave* of Zuane Paisi (son of Stamati) as *sindico* of Anogi.³⁹ Orders made in response to the petition by Galati issued by the *provveditor* of Cephalonia recognise the ‘irregular election’ and the ‘serious detriment and prejudice’ which it threatened ‘to the appellant and to the legal rights of the Conclave

Papakosta, *Το αρχείο των Βενετών προβλέπτων της Πρέβεζας: διοίκηση της πόλης τον 18ο αιώνα* (Περιφέρεια Ηπείρου–Περιφερειακή Ενότητα Πρέβεζας, 2018), 176.

³⁵ Karavias Grivas, *Ιστορία της νήσου Ίθάκης*, 73.

³⁶ The reference of 1791 in a series of letters in ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, «Σπαράγματα», Box 26, Fragments attributable to Eugenio Loverdo (1791), ff. [1]–[3]. The reference of 1794 in a response to a petition in ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, «Σπαράγματα», Box 30, [Unattributed *filze suffragi*], issued by Carlo Antonio Marin *provveditor* of Cephalonia, dated 12 December 1794.

³⁷ As described in Nikias, ‘The archive’, 75.

³⁸ ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, «Σπαράγματα», Box 26, Fragments attributable to Eugenio Loverdo (1791), ff. [1]–[3].

³⁹ ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, «Σπαράγματα», Box 30, [Unattributed *filze suffragi*], issued by Carlo Antonio Marin *provveditor* of Cephalonia, dated 12 December 1794. This is the brother of Cristodulo Galati, father of the pre-revolutionary figure Nikolaos Galatis.

itself'.⁴⁰ The foundation of the Council or *Conclave* clearly provided a forum for the contestation of social tensions between rival clans and factions, a subject which must be taken up by future study of the documents.⁴¹ It is probably not a coincidence that the two references to the body which have been located among the Venetian-period documents both concern disputes among the highest stratum of local officeholders, the *sindici*.

Formally speaking, the evidence of the institution of the Council or *Conclave* signifies another shift in power. Just a few years after the power of election was moved from the visiting Venetian counsellor to the jurisdiction of the governor (in 1781), this power was then put in the hands of a newly instituted body composed of prominent Ithacesians who were presumably selected on the basis of certain criteria in line with Venetian practice.⁴² In the words of a later administrator, the institution of the

⁴⁰ 'come da elezione irregolare e cose tutte malamente, indelitamente seguite a grave danno e pregiudicio del sudetto appelante e dei dritti legali del conclave medesimo': *ibid.*

⁴¹ See the fascinating recent work on this topic, based on evidence from the State Archives of Venice, in Kapodistrias, 'Οι λύκοι που κατασπάραζαν τα πρόβατα'. On these themes in the better studied case of Cephalonia, see, e.g., Despina Vlassi, 'Συγκρούσεις οικογενειών και μηχανισμοί εξουσίας στη βενετοκρατούμενη Κεφαλονιά', in *Πρακτικά Ζ' Πανιόνιο Συνέδριο, Λευκάδα, 26–30 Μαΐου 2002*, vol. 2 (Εταιρεία Λευκαδικών Μελετών, 2004), 463–66.

⁴² Generally on the subject of the formation of civic communities and their institutions in the Venetian possessions in the Greek-speaking territories, see Anastasia Papadia-Lala, *Ο θεσμός των αστικών κοινοτήτων στον ελληνικό χώρο κατά την περίοδο της βενετοκρατίας, 13ος–18ος αι.: μια συνθετική προσέγγιση* (Ελληνικό Ινστιτούτο Βυζαντινών και Μεταβυζαντινών Σπουδών Βενετίας, 2004); and a more concise survey in Anastasia Papadia-Lala, 'Κοινωνική συγκρότηση στις πόλεις', in *Βενετοκρατούμενη Ελλάδα: Προσεγγίζοντας την ιστορία της*, ed. Chrysa A. Maltezos, vol. 1 (Ελληνικό Ινστιτούτο Βυζαντινών και Μεταβυζαντινών Σπουδών Βενετίας, 2010), 105–30. With broader scope, also relevant is Anastasia Papadia-Lala, 'Society, Administration and Identities in Latin Greece', in *A Companion to Latin Greece*, ed. Nickiphoros I. Tsougarakis and Peter Lock (Brill, 2014), 114–44. An important treatment of rural society in Kostas Lambrinos, 'Κοινωνική συγκρότηση στην ύπαιθρο', in *Βενετοκρατούμενη Ελλάδα: Προσεγγίζοντας την ιστορία της*, ed. Chrysa A. Maltezos, vol. 1 (Ελληνικό Ινστιτούτο Βυζαντινών και Μεταβυζαντινών Σπουδών Βενετίας, 2010), 131–54. With specific focus on rural Cephalonia: Despina Vlassi, 'Κοινωνική και οικονομική συγκρότηση του ορεινού χώρου στη βενετοκρατούμενη Κεφαλονιά', in *Κοινωνίες της υπαίθρου στην ελληνοβενετική Ανατολή (13ος–18ος αι.)*, ed.

deliberative body in Ithaca under Erizzo established a ‘kind of Nobility’ on the island.⁴³ Indeed the establishment of the council, as the culmination of years of reforms, signifies the constitution of a formally defined elite through its own political organ, with the handful of *sindici* sitting at the top. Already by the 1770s the *sindici* were singled out in lists of elected officers by use of the honorific *Dottor* (as shown in the list of *sindici* in the Appendix), and Greek-language documents from the 1780s even speak of ‘the noble *sindici*’ (‘ι ευγενίς σιντιχι’), distinguishing these highest local officeholders from their peers.⁴⁴

The expansion of the powers of the Ithacesian *sindici* represents the response of the law to the island’s social and economic development. Considered in the context of the constitutional history surveyed, the establishment of the Council or *Conclave* in the late 1780s was one stage in a long reformatory process. This negotiated the rising influence of a growing local elite in Ithaca and the tension this created with a constitutional structure that had put power in the hands of a governor picked among the elite of a neighbouring island. The reforms of the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries, considered together, mark the slow but steady increase of the role of Ithacesians in the administration of this tiny Venetian colony at the frontier of the Empire. While the reforms instituting a deliberative body and giving it a right to elect the highest officers would appear towards the end of the three centuries of Venetian rule, this would be the mature form of a trend which we have traced over three centuries. Through several petitions addressed by the Ithacesians to the Venetian authorities, beginning in the late sixteenth century, the Ithacesians raised their voice about the government of their island and demanded a role in

Kostas E Lambrinos (Research Centre for Medieval and Modern Hellenism of the Academy of Athens, 2018).

⁴³ ‘qualche forma di Nobiltà a questo paese’: Livitsanis, ‘Το «Λίμπρο ντ’ Όρο» του 1799’, 205 n. 36. Cf. Nikias, ‘Class and society’.

⁴⁴ ‘ι ευγενίς σιντιχι του Νισιου ετουτουνου’: ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, «Σπαράγματα», Box 37, Fragments attributable to Zuanne Anino (1784), f. [353]. Also see, in an earlier document of 1763, reference to ‘ἀρχοντες συντήχοι’ (of Vathy), and to the ‘προεστούς και κάπους τών φαμελιώνε ετουτουνού του χωριου βαθθ’: ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, vol. Valliano Metaxà (1763–4, i), f. 83r. Accents reproduced as in the original.

administration. The history of the reforms which responded to these demands reveals a brewing tension between the established governing structure over Ithaca and the slowly rising power of a local elite made up of Ithacians of growing wealth who held influence over the island's society. By the late eighteenth century the island had developed social and economic inequalities which followed the growth of the island's population (from 903 souls in 1583 to 6,844 in 1807) and the expansion of its productive economy.⁴⁵ It must remain for future research to uncover this process in greater detail through diligent study of the large volume of relevant documents which reveal the function of the *sindici* in administration, and portray their role in local affairs as prominent elites of their communities.

III. The civic offices (*cariche urbane*) in their social context

The offices of the local administration elected in Ithaca were the *sindici*, *provveditori alla sanità*, *giustizieri*, *deputati alle strade*, *deputati all'estime*, *contestabili*, and *cartofori*. This body of offices must have been established already by the first surviving list of 1655, and there is no substantive change to the titles elected over the next century and a half (other than variations of form between, say, *provveditori*, *procuratori* and *deputati alla sanità*, or between *signori* and *deputati alle strade*). The *sindici* were the most important and influential of the officers, and as we have seen, they had a role in the election of the others in lower roles even before the substantial reforms of the late eighteenth century. Pending further study, we can only assume that the roles of these officers in Ithaca emulated the functions that

⁴⁵ The population statistics in Gerasimos Livitsanis, 'The village of Stravonikou and the population of Ithaca in the 1583 census of Kastroylakas: Re-reading an old source in search of Venetian Ithaca', *Bulletin of the Ithacan Historical Society* 1 (2023): 48–56; Ioanna Athanasopoulou, *Ο πληθυσμός της Ιθάκης, του Καλάμου και του Κάστου το έτος 1807: έκδοση της απογραφής με τίτλο Anagrafi degli abitanti dell'isola d'itaca e dei scogli adjacenti di calamo e castus* (Ίδρυμα Κεφαλονιάς και Ιθάκης/Ίόνιος Εταιρεία Ιστορικών Μελετών, 2019), 3. Some discussion of the social trends in Nikias, 'The Venetian Governor's Palace on Ithaca'. Also Kapodistrias, 'Οι λύκοι που κατασπάράζαν τα πρόβατα'.

officers of the same name had in the other Venetian communities.⁴⁶ Interestingly, when we compare the bodies of offices elected by the Councils of the civic communities in the larger centres of the region under Venetian rule, there are always variations to the list which betray the fact that the establishment of each of the offices probably responded to different local factors and administrative needs. A striking example is offered by the case of the Zacynthian officers charged with auditing transactions with Jews (*scontro delli Hebrei*), which represented the attempt of the state to closely monitor the participation of Jews in the trading economy.⁴⁷ Put simply, in the organisation of the offices, as in other instances, the Venetian system provided a grammar of public administration which was flexible and adapted to local circumstance in practice.

We cannot survey the role of all the offices here in detail, which we leave for closer study of the particular series of documents relevant to the respective offices. Though I have focussed on the role of the *sindici* as the highest officeholders, other officers also played an important role in the

⁴⁶ Generally on the local offices see the survey in Papadaki, ‘Τοπικοί αξιωματούχοι και υπάλληλοι’. Note, however, the passage on Ithaca at p. 92 is inaccurate, being derived from Karavias Grivas. Detailed studies of the local offices in the various Venetian possessions are scattered. On the administration of rural Cephalonia, see Vlasi, ‘Κοινωνική και οικονομική συγκρότηση’. For those elected in the ‘city’ by the reformed Council of 150 in Cephalonia after 1753, see Vlasi, ‘Το Συμβούλιο των 150’, 164 n. 19. For Zakynthos, see the extensive study of the offices elected by the Council of 150 in the sixteenth century in Panagiota Tzivara, *Βενετοκρατούμενη Ζάκυνθος, 1588–1594: η νομή και η διαχείριση της εξουσίας από το Συμβούλιο των 150* (Ενάλιος, 2009), 117–69; also Marianna Kolyvã, ‘Κοινοτικοί θεσμοί στον αστικό και αγροτικό χώρο της Ζακύνθου (16ος-17ος αι.)’, *Μεσαιωνικά και Νέα Ελληνικά* 11 (2014): 49–68. On the elite in Lefkada, with reference to local officeholders: Efi Argyrou, ‘Γαιοκτητική ελίτ στη Λευκάδα το 18ο αιώνα’, in *Πρακτικά του Θ’ Πανιωνίου Συνεδρίου, Παξοί 26–30 Μαΐου 2010*, ed. Alikì D Nikiforou, vol. 1 (Εταιρεία Παξινών Μελετών, 2014), 254. An important approach to the peripheral cases of Parga, Preveza, and Vonitza in Christina E Papakosta, ‘Πάργα, Πρέβεζα, Βόνιτσα: Αστικές συσσωματώσεις στα Βενετικά Ηπειρωτικά εξαρτήματα’, *Εώα και Εσπέρια* 7 (2007): 213–32. Also generally on local administration in the Ionian in the late eighteenth century, see Dimitris Arvanitakis, ‘Προβλήματα κοινοτικής αυτοδιοίκησης και κοινωνικές αντιθέσεις στον Ιόνιο χώρο (1750–1797)’, in *Ελληνοισμός και Κάτω Ιταλία. Από τα Ιόνια νησιά στην Grecia salentina*, vol. 1 (Ιόνιο Πανεπιστήμιο, 2002), 9–54.

⁴⁷ See Tzivara, *Βενετοκρατούμενη Ζάκυνθος*, 166–68.

daily function of the state apparatus in Ithaca. Particular significance was given generally in the administration of the maritime empire to public health. This also involved the local administrators.⁴⁸ The *provveditori* or *deputati alla sanità* (in Greek, *σανιτᾶδες*) always rank after the *sindici* in the lists of electees, and are sometimes grouped together as in one proclamation of 1675 which speaks of the ‘Sindici, Sanità, e Primati di quest’Isola’.⁴⁹ These officers of public health were particularly significant functionaries, for they were the face of the state in its regulation of the movement of people and goods, which was key in the mitigation of outbreaks of disease brought to the island through merchant trade by sea. These *provveditori alla sanità* oversaw the daily supervision and monitoring of maritime movement at offices located at the ports (called *uffici di sanità*). In Ithaca, these were based at the southern port of Vathy (the *molo di Vati*), and in the north of the island at Kioni (*Chioni*) and Frikes (*Frichies*) serving maritime trade with the hilltop towns of Anogi and Exogi respectively.⁵⁰

While the body of offices elected in Ithaca emulates the model of the larger Venetian communities, it does not mean there were not local differences of substance. Indeed, one office elected at Ithaca, the *cartofori* (*χαρτοφόροι*) — not attested in any of the other Venetian communities considered by the scholarship — makes an interesting appearance in Ithaca which begs an explanation. These ‘paper-bearers’ are grouped together with the *contestabili* in the sources, sometimes even being elected together.⁵¹ Rosters for the daily service of the *contestabili* and *cartofori* note

⁴⁸ Katerina Konstantinidou, ‘Gli uffici di sanità delle Isole Ionie durante il Seicento e il Settecento’, *Studi Veneziani* 49 (2005): 379–91.

⁴⁹ ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, «Σπαράγματα», Box 8, *Proclama* of Francesco Cologna (1 January 1675).

⁵⁰ The function of the offices of *sanità* in Ithaca has been described in Giannis S Vlassopoulos, *Ανεμοκάραβα: Καράβια, εμπόριο, μεταφορές, ληστείες, Πειρατές, Πανώλη στο Ιόνιο και στα Ακαρνικά παράλια τον 18ο αιώνα* (Φήμιος–Δημοτικές Πολιτιστικές Εκδηλώσεις Ιθάκης, 2006), at 24–26, 34–35, 42–44.

⁵¹ For example, in the list of elected officers of 1709, the *contestabili e cartofori* of Anogi are simply listed together without distinction: ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, vol. G. Assani (1708–9, i), ff. 28r–29v, at f. 29r.

the days and locations of service for those appointed to the task.⁵² We assume that the *contestabili* functioned in the manner of their peers in other places, that is, as officers of public order with various responsibilities in the judicial process.⁵³ What their colleagues in the *cartofori* did remains unclear. We might imagine they served as messengers, as their name suggests, though we must await further study into this Ithacan peculiarity.

The difference of greatest significance between the Ithacan system and the better studied arrangements of the local administrations in the larger civic communities under Venetian rule concerns the social status of the officeholders. In the civic communities the elected offices were a source of prestige and were much desired by the limited body of citizens (*cittadini*) who had a right to be elected to them through the civic councils. Indeed the very governorship of Ithaca was —formally speaking— an office of the Cephalonian local administration elected among other posts by the civic community.⁵⁴ In Ithaca there can be no doubt that the holders of the highest offices, the *sindici*, were figures of significant local prominence in a small island society, and that the office imparted them with an authority or perhaps gave sanction to their abuses. However, can we be sure that the lower offices were a source of prestige in the same way? In rural Cephalonia, even the office of *contestabile* was sought-after by village elders whose service in the role exempted them from the contribution of compulsory labour to the state and marked them out from their peers with a status of

⁵² In the volume of the governor Diorzi (served 1655–56) there is a roster (*Descricon delli Contestabili e Cartofori*) which provides that ‘Domenicha tutti li Contestabili e Cartovori devono esser in Palaz[zo]’: ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, vol. Alessandro Diorzi (1654–56), f. 186r. Each day’s roster posted one *contestabile* together with one *cartoforo*. While the roster is undated, the names match those in the election of 1655.

⁵³ On the Cephalonian *contestabili* in rural areas, presumably the model for the office established in Ithaca, see Vlassi, ‘Κοινωνική και οικονομική συγκρότηση’, 136–39.

⁵⁴ Despite the formal legal status of the governorship of Ithaca, I have argued that in practice the governors behaved as representatives of Venice who ran a *reggimento* in miniature: Nikias, ‘The Governors’; idem, ‘The archive’; idem, ‘The Venetian Governor’s Palace on Ithaca’. On the status of the local offices in the civic communities generally, see above n. 42.

relative significance in their community.⁵⁵ Were Ithaca's *contestabili* the same? The evidence suggests otherwise.

A most striking discovery among the Venetian documents from Ithaca is a considerable number of petitions to the authorities from Ithacesians who complain that they have been improperly appointed to posts unbefitting of their status. The lower offices were not so much a desired opportunity to participate in the administration of the island, but were appointed as burdens of compulsory service to the state (*angaria personale*).⁵⁶ Members of families who claimed exemptions from the *angarie* sought to be relieved of their appointments to the lowest offices. The examples are numerous and here it suffices to state a few which indicate the breadth of exemptions claimed. The case of Stati Servò, who was freed from an appointment as *contestabile* in 1739, shows that residents of Ithaca who descended from a Cephalonian family with the civil rights of the *cittadini* were unable to be burdened with the low offices.⁵⁷ Some Ithacesian families had similar privileges. In 1787 the governor retracted the nomination of Spiro Alevrà Corialò for the office of *contestabile*, having been informed by the *sindici* that his family's status (as a 'Famiglia Civile') meant that he was exempt.⁵⁸ Some families claiming such exemptions (called *privileggiati*) traced them back several centuries: for example, the Pugliese (Πουλιέζος), whose members claimed privileges as descendants of

⁵⁵ Vlasi, 'Κοινωνική και οικονομική συγκρότηση', 136–37.

⁵⁶ On *angarie* see Konstantinos Dokos, 'Οι αστικές κοινότητες και οι αργαρείες του δημοσίου στη βενετοκρατούμενη Πελοπόννησο', *Εώα και Εσπέρια* 4 (1999–2000): 243–81.

⁵⁷ 'Rapresenta à questa Carica Stati Servò oriundo da quest'Isola, che non ostante di famiglia citadina ... venga molestato da cottesti abbitanti sino ad'essere nottato per contestabile: incarichiamo la Spetabilità Vostra à rimuovere quest'inconvenienti che sono offensivi al dillui carattere civile': ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, vol. Giovanni Cambici (1739–40), *Filze lettere*, f. 1146 (Letter of the *provveditor* of Cephalonia Nicolò Boldù dated 24 September 1739).

⁵⁸ 'Essendo Stato informato dalli Signori Sindici, che Spiro Alevrà Corialò è, d'una Famiglia Civile, e che alcuno delli loro Individui, non abbia mai servito per Contestabile, per ciò avendo nominato in detto Servizio, ritrata la nomina stessa': ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, «Σπαράγματα», Box 24, [*Libro straordinario*(?) attributable to Theodoro Assani (1787)], ff. 16r–v (act dated 19 February 1788).

the old governor Costa Puiese (who served 1536–63);⁵⁹ and the Galati, whose privileges were first conferred under the rule of the Tocco (1357–1479) and recognised through Venetian rule.⁶⁰ The names of several other families we must leave for further study. The systematic study of these documents will provide new evidence for social inequalities and their recognition in law.

Considered together, the evidence surveyed here allows us to trace the emergence of prominent clans in the three settlement areas of the Ithaca during Venetian rule.⁶¹ The list of *sindici* presented in the Appendix below allows us to peer onto the society of seventeenth and eighteenth-century Ithaca. While a closer treatment with reference to other evidence is needed, we can sketch some of the trends in the family names which reappear several times in the list.⁶² During the seventeenth century, the *sindici* of the main township of Vathy (*Vatì*) in the south were supplied mainly by the families Caravià, Petalà, and Dendrinò. By the late eighteenth century, the

⁵⁹ See above n. 11.

⁶⁰ ‘Emerge da pubblici documenti andar esente da angarie personali codesta Famiglia Galati. E venendomi esposto per parte di Dottor Niccolò Galati disendente della mentovata Famiglia esser stato lui medesimo agravato dal basso carico di Contestabile [incar]icar deggio la Spetabilità Vostra renderlo tolto libero dall’incompetente agravio, ingiurioso al [...] indulto e lesivo il di lui privile[g]gio.’: ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, «Σπαράγματα», Box 19, [*Filze lettere*], no. 9 (letter of the *provveditor* of Cephalonia Domenego Muazzo dated 22 February 1787). A survey of the old evidence for the privileges of the Galati, written while the Archive of Ithaca was closed, in Kyriaco Nikias, ‘Class and society in Ithaca under Tocco and early Venetian rule (1357–ca. 1600)’, *Byzantine and Modern Greek Studies* 47, no. 1 (2023): 54–70; cf. Prevezianos, ‘Ψάχνοντας για την Ιθάκη’, 103. See comments on new unpublished evidence in K. Nikias, ‘Sources for the history of Ithaca after antiquity: ca. 530–1500’ [REGESTA ITHACAE HISTORIAE, I], *Bulletin of the Ithacan Historical Society* 1 (2023): 63 n. 18.

⁶¹ On the settlement patterns in the Venetian period see Gerasimos Livitsanis, ‘Πόσο οικείο μας είναι το πρώιμο πρόσφατο παρελθόν; Προς μια αρχαιολογία της Βενετοκρατούμενης Ιθάκης’, in *Πρακτικά του ΙΑ΄ Διεθνούς Πανιωνίου Συνεδρίου*, ed. Dora F. Markatou, vol. 5 (Argostoli: Εταιρεία Κεφαλληνιακών Ιστορικών Ερευνών, 2020), 565–79; Nikias, ‘The Venetian Governor’s Palace on Ithaca’.

⁶² On the surnames of Ithaca, see the inventory compiled with reference to several sources in George Paxinos, *Passage to Ithaca: History, Surnames, Identity*, 2nd ed. (Ithacan Historical Society, 2022).

Draculi and Savò (a branch of the Petalà) were predominant.⁶³ This documentary evidence corroborates the accounts of the early travellers to the island who most often met with the most prominent figures in its political and economic life.⁶⁴ Costantin Savo, son of Vettor (*sindico* in 1784), is the long-time vice-consul of the United Kingdom who provided lodging for the visiting antiquarians Sir William Gell and William Martin Leake in the first years of the nineteenth century.⁶⁵ Other figures outside these clans must have been significant figures in their own right, such as Demetrio Solomon (*sindico* in 1763) who served as a public archivist, and Michiel Roditi (*sindico* in 1796) who practised as a notary.⁶⁶ In the north of the island, the large part of the *sindici* of the town of Anogi (*Anoi*) were members of the families Paisi and Galati. Noteworthy are the appearances of Zorzi Galati (*sindico* in 1696 and 1709), his son Zaneto (*sindico* in 1753, 1757, 1761, 1763) and grandson, the notary Cristodulo (*sindico* in 1777). These were the great-grandfather, grandfather, and father of the notorious figure of the prerevolutionary period Nikolaos Galatis.⁶⁷ In the other northern town of Exogi (*Oxoi*) the family Vrettò appears to have had tight

⁶³ That the Draculi are a branch of the Dendrinò is perhaps suggested by the gradual reduction in the number of Dendrinò in the list of *sindici*, who give way to figures with the double-barrelled name Dendrinò Draculi, and later simply to Draculi. However this relation is not described in Alexandros S Santas, *Η έξ'Ιθάκης οικογένεια Δρακούλη* (Τύποις «Χρυσσαυγή», 1958). That the Savò are a branch of the Petalà was already recorded by Leake: William Martin Leake, *Travels in Northern Greece*, vol. 3 (J. Rodwell, 1835), 28.

⁶⁴ Leake, *Travels in Northern Greece*, 3:28.

⁶⁵ William Gell, *The Geography and Antiquities of Ithaca* (Longman, Hurst, Rees, and Orme, 1807), 27; Leake, *Travels in Northern Greece*, 3:25. Costantino Savo is listed as son of Vettor, who had also been vice-consul, on whom see Kapodistrias, 'Οι λύκοι που κατασπάραζαν τα πρόβατα', 657ff.

⁶⁶ On the archivist Demetrio Solomon, see Nikias, 'The archive', 74. One register of the notary Michiel Roditi survives: Ελληνικό Λογοτεχνικό και Ιστορικό Αρχείο (ΕΛΙΑ), Νοταριακοί κώδικες Ιθάκης, κωδ. 14 (Μιχαήλ Ροδίτης).

⁶⁷ The familial relation is made out by their record in the census of 1807: Athanasopoulou, *Ο πληθυσμός της Ιθάκης*, 224. Cristodulo Galati (b. ca. 1752 according to the census) was a notary with five surviving registers: ΓΑΚ-ΤΙ, Νοταριακό Αρχείο, Φ. 54. He was appointed *protonotarios* in 1792: Nikias, 'Private legal practice and public authority in early Venetian Ithaca', 23 n. 88. On Nikolaos Galatis (1792–1819) see Eleftherios Moraitinis-Patriarcheas, *Νικόλαος Γαλάτης ο Φιλικός* (Kedros, 2002).

control over the office, reflecting its local dominance which had been observed by both Gell and Leake.⁶⁸ The prominent figures of late eighteenth century continued to hold sway in the island's society into the turbulent years after the fall of Venetian rule in 1797. The surviving *sindici* of the Venetian period, as the local elite under the old regime, were recognised among the new 'nobility' established under the provisional constitution of 1799, which is presented for the first time in this volume by Gerasimos Livitsanis.⁶⁹ Their names reappear once more under the Septinsular Republic in the *libro d'oro* of 1803.⁷⁰ Considered together, these sources shall no doubt offer themselves to many further studies which shall shed light on the people of Venetian Ithaca, a community until now overlooked in accounts of the Early Modern history of Greece.

⁶⁸ Gell, *The Geography and Antiquities of Ithaca*, 109; Leake, *Travels in Northern Greece*, 3:25.

⁶⁹ Livitsanis, 'Το «Λίμπρο ντ' Όρο» του 1799'.

⁷⁰ Eleni F. Griva, *To Libro d'Oro της Ιθάκης* (Εταιρεία Κεφαλληνιακών Ιστορικών Ερευνών, 1997); Georgios N Moschopoulos, 'Τò Libro d'Όρο στὴν Ἐπτάνησο (Ειδήσεις ἀπὸ ἐπίσημα ἔγγραφα καὶ ὁ κώδικας τῆς Ἰθάκης)', *Ἄνθη Χαρίτων* 18 (1998): 395–409.

Figures

Figure 1: The first folio of the list of elected officers of 29 March 1655.
 Source: ΓΑΚ-ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, vol. Α. Diorzi (1654-6), f. 664r.

522¹⁷

Correr
 Antonio Agio
 Panagiot. Vico d. Pato
 Chetoni. Leata
 Panagiot. Pappas

Ad. 30 March 1680

Il M^o. P. Correr e V. Correr in questa Vitis del
 Ibechi stando terminata la sua Vitis e che
 molti d. quest. habbano habb. d'ordine da S. M.
 dicit. mandaa e suffigi, e io rimesso al cogn^o. S. M.
 a questo g^o. P. Correr e V. Correr. L'ordine per
 dicit. fassa da S. M. comanda e preta. che
 n. sia alterata in alcuna maniera ma debba
 honore sua debba honore la sua giornal d'anno
 come sta e gia.

Todero Correr V. Cons. V. Correr

Figure 2: The last folio of the list of elected officers of 30 March 1680 bearing the signature of the visiting Venetian counsellor Thodoro Correr. Correr signs Todero, but the preamble to the election gives Thodoro. Source: ΓAK-TI, AΒΔ, vol. S. Lusi (1679–80), f. 522r.

Appendix

List of *sindici* of Ithaca (1649–1796)

Note on the lists

The below names of *sindici* are extracted from lists of election of Ithacesians who held minor posts in the administration of the island under Venetian rule. Until 1781 the lists were redacted by the visiting Venetian counsellors, with an official copy provided to the chancellery of Ithaca, where they survive today in the archive of the Venetian-period governors of the island. After 1781 the elections were undertaken by the governors, and their fate during the last decade of Venetian rule remains opaque, as explained above. The names recorded for 1649, 1674, 1703, 1776, 1796 are taken from other sources, including notarial acts and official correspondence where the *sindici* are mentioned. The lists are written in Italian and the effect of Venetian phonology can occlude some of the Greek names, but Latinate names are rather common (e.g. *Alvise, Danal, Marc Antonio*).

For simplicity the names have been transcribed in full without indicating where abbreviations are used by the copyist; where illegible or damaged, reconstructions have been noted with square brackets [].

<i>quondam</i>	Denotes name of father where deceased.
<i>de/di</i>	Denotes name of father where alive; in fewer instances, comma used for same.

[1649]

<i>Vathy</i>	<i>Anogi</i>	<i>Exogi</i>
Αντώνης Πεταλάς	-	-
Σταμάτης Μαρούλης		

Stamatoula Zapanti, ed., *Γεώργιος Βλασόπουλος: Νοτάριος Βαθέος Ιθάκης, 1636–1648* (Γενικά Αρχεία του Κράτους, 2002), 261.

[1655]

<i>Vatby</i>	<i>Anogi</i>	<i>Exogi</i>
Draco Petalla	Gerolimo ⁷¹ Callinico	Vinier Vretto
Danalli Marulli	Micali Paisi	Gabriel Gavrilli
Thoma Dendrino	Zafiri Paisi de Costantin	

ΓAK–TI, ABΔ, vol. A. Diorzi (1654–6), ff. 664r–665r
(Election by *consiglier et vice gerente* Piero Balbi, 29 March 1655)

[1669]

<i>Vatby</i>	<i>Anogi</i>	<i>Exogi</i>
Thoma Dendrino	Jani Schiotti	Giorgo Mavromati, Nicolo
Zagni Petala	Constantin Paisi	Andrea Gavrili
Thoma Caravia		

[Gerolimo Calinico
Janni Sichiotti]⁷²

ΓAK–TI, ABΔ, vol. G.B. Metaxà (1668–73, ii) ff. 139r–140v
(Election by *consiglier et vice gerente* Francesco Pasqualigo, 19 March 1669)

⁷¹ Reconstructed from Ger^{mo}. This could alternatively be Gerasimo, however Gerolimo Callinico is attested in full in other elections, e.g. the election of ‘Jani Calinico <quondam/di> Gerolimo’ as *giusticier* of Anogi in ΓAK–TI, ABΔ, vol. G.B. Metaxà (1668–73, ii), f. 139v.

⁷² There are two copies of the election dated 19 August 1669 with minor variations between them, suggesting revisions were perhaps made by the time of the second copy. From the acts before and after the copies, it seems that the earlier copy is that in ΓAK–TI, ABΔ, vol. G.B. Metaxà (1668–73, ii) ff. 139r–140v; and the later copy that in ΓAK–TI, ABΔ, vol. G.B. Metaxà (1668–71, i), ff. 74v–75v. The names of the *sindici* of Anogi in the later copy are listed in square brackets here.

[1670]

<i>Vathy</i>	<i>Anogi</i>	<i>Exogi</i>
Statti Pettala	Miliaresi Paisi	Nicolo Vretto di Nadal
Draco Caravia	Galano Galatti	Alfonso Vretto, Nuzzo
Giorgo Micalopulo		

ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, vol. G.B. Metaxà (1668–73, i), ff. 85v–87r
(Election by *consigliere et vice gerente* Marin Donà, 27 March 1670)

[1671]

<i>Vathy</i>	<i>Anogi</i>	<i>Exogi</i>
Thoma Dendrino	Gerolimo Calinico	Danal Vretto
Janni Caravia quondam Marcantonio	Costantin Paisi	Bartolo Gavrili
Nicolo Petala quondam Dimo		

ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, «Σπαράγματα», Box 8, Fragments of G.B. Metaxà.
(Election by *consigliere et vice gerente* Matio Querini, 31 March 1671)

[1672]

<i>Vathy</i>	<i>Anogi</i>	<i>Exogi</i>
Draco Caravia	Thomà Raftopulo	Nicolo Vreto de Na[dal]
Janni Petala de Draco	Andruzzo Galati	Andrea G[avr]il[i] ⁷³
Andrea Dendrino de Draco		

ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, «Σπαράγματα», Box 8, Fragments of G.B. Metaxà.
(Election by *consigliere et vice gerente* Vincenzo Da Riva, 28 March 1672)

⁷³ The folio is heavily damaged; the names have been reconstructed from context.

[1674]

<i>Vathy</i>	<i>Anogi</i>	<i>Exogi</i>
Draco Caravia	Vico Galati	Nicolo Vretto di Danal
Janni Petala quondam Draco	Thomà Raftopulo	Nicolo Maurochefalo
Andrea Dendrinò di Draculi		

ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, vol. F. Colonia (1673–5, ii), *Filze lettere*, f.nn.
(A list of *sindici* in a proclamation of the governor, 4 July 1674)

[1675]

<i>Vathy</i>	<i>Anogi</i>	<i>Exogi</i>
Thoma Dendrinò	Gerolimo Calinico	Cristodulo Vreto di Nadal
Draco Caravia	Janni Sichiòti	Bortolo Gavriili
Matio Petala quondam Demo		

ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, vol. F. Colonia (1673–5, I), ff. 76v–77v
(Election by *consiglier et vice gerente* Vincenzo Donado, 29 March 1675)

[1680]

<i>Vathy</i>	<i>Anogi</i>	<i>Exogi</i>
Jani Vlasopulo quondam Carlo	Jani Sichiòti Lusi Paxino	Cristodulo Vretto di Nadal
Thoma Caravia Anastasio Petala di Nicolò		Demetrio Vretto di Zagni

ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, vol. S. Lusi (1679–80), ff. 520v–522r
(Election by *consiglier et vice gerente* Thodoro Correr, 30 March 1680)

[1683]

<i>Vathy</i>	<i>Anogi</i>	<i>Exogi</i>
Janni Caravia quondam Marc Antonio	Migliaressi Paisi Lusi Paxinò	Nicolo Vreto di Nadal Bortolo Gavrili
Stathi Dendrinò Foli		
Janni Petala di Draco		

ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, vol. T. Dalladecima (1682–3), ff. 278r–280v
(Election by *consigliere et vice gerente* Maffio Badoer, 30 March 1683)

[1685]

<i>Vathy</i>	<i>Anogi</i>	<i>Exogi</i>
Thomà Dendrinò	Lusi Passino	Nicolo Vreto di Nadal
Janni Petalà di Draco	Janni Sichiothi	Bartolo Gavrili
Thomà Marulli		

ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, «Σπαράγματα», Box 38, Fragments of Domenico Corafan
(Election by *consigliere et vice gerente* Beneto Bolani, 31 March 1685)

[1690]

<i>Vathy</i>	<i>Anogi</i>	<i>Exogi</i>
Battista Solomon	Migliaressi Paisi	Jani Vreto di Battista
Marc Antonio Caravia quondam Thoma	Costantin Galati Lusi Paxino	Alfonso Petala
Alevisè Petala Spazza		
Valiano Dendrinò		

ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, «Σπαράγματα», Box 38, Fragments of Giacomo Metaxà.
(Election by *consigliere et vice gerente* Zan Andrea Loredan, 31 March 1690)

[1691]

<i>Vathy</i>	<i>Anogi</i>	<i>Exogi</i>
Andrea Dendrinó	Nicolò Paxinò	[Bo]rtolo Gavrili
Draco Caraviá	Giorgo Sichiotti	Antonio Vrettò di Stamatello
Janni Pettalà Dra[culi]	Menego Paisi Migliaressi	

Alivise Vlassopulo

ΓAK–TI, ABA, vol. N. Pignator (1690), *Suppliche*, ff. 984–985
(Election by *consigliere et vice gerente* Bernardin Lippomano, 31 March 1691)

[1693]

<i>Vathy</i>	<i>Anogi</i>	<i>Exogi</i>
Alvise Petalla Spazza	Lusi Paxino	Christodulo Vretto
Giorgo Ferendino Carvuni	Giorgo Galati d'Andruzzo	Alfonso Petalla
Draco Caravia	Paolo Paisi	

Zannetto Vlisma

ΓAK–TI, ABA, vol. A. Corafan (1692–3), ff. 26r–28r
(Election by *consigliere et vice gerente* Giulio Donà, 31 March 1693)

[1696]

<i>Vathy</i>	<i>Anogi</i>	<i>Exogi</i>
Nicolo Trupo	Thodorin Callinico	Zanni Prossalendi
Marc Antonio Caravia quondam Thoma	Zorzi Gallati Thodorin Paxino	Anzoletto Raftopullo di Costantin

Zaneto Vlisma

ΓAK–TI, ABA, vol. D. Corafan (1695–6), ff. 269v–272r
(Election by *consigliere et vice gerente* Zanfrancesco Barbaro, 31 March 1696)

[1703]

<i>Vathy</i>	<i>Anogi</i>	<i>Exogi</i>
μισέρ Αντρια Δεντρινο	Θοδορι Γάλατι ποτε	-
μισέρ Αναγνωστι Δεντρινο	Νικολου	
μισέρ Αλιβιζι Πεταλα	Νικολο Παξινο ποτε	
μισέρ Αναστασι Πεταλα	Θοδορι	
μισέρ Αποστολι Καραβια	Γιανι Μαρουδα ποτε	
μισέρ Αναστασι Στεφανιτζι	Αντρια	
	Θοδορι Καλινικο	
	Γιοργο Σικιοτι	
	Νικολο Παιζι	

ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, vol. D. Volterra (1703–4, i), ff. 233r–234v
(List of officeholders «ονοματολογι», without other details of election, 11 May 1703). The large number of officers demands caution. By comparison with earlier lists, it is likely that several persons listed here were past *sindici*.

[1704]

<i>Vathy</i>	<i>Anogi</i>	<i>Exogi</i>
Andrea Dendrino	Janni Paisi di Paolo	Paolo Vreto
Anastasio Petalla Savò	Stelio Paxino	Chico Vreto
Apostogli Caravia	quondam Thodorin	
quondam Janni	Janni Maruda	
	quondam Andrea	

ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, vol. D. Voltera (1703–4, ii), ff. 253v–254v
(Election by *consigliar et vice gerente* Lucio Da Riva, 30 March 1704)

[1709]

<i>Vathy</i>	<i>Anogi</i>	<i>Exogi</i>
Giorgo Petala di Janni	Zorzi Galati	Giorgo Vreto
Francesco Solomon ⁷⁴	Menegho Paisi	quondam Battista
	Giorgo Sichiotti	Anastasio Raftopulo

ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, vol. G. Assani (1708–9, i), ff. 28r–29v
(Election by *consigliere et vice gerente* Giovanni Giacomo Querini,
[March] 1709)

[1712]

<i>Vathy</i>	<i>Anogi</i>	<i>Exogi</i>
Alevisse Vlassopullo	Janni Paisi	...]o Vreto
Condari Petalla	Giorgo Gallati	... Mavrochef]allo
Menego Dendrinò	Nicolo Paxino	d'Alfonso ⁷⁵
	Levendi	

ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, «Σπαράγματα», Box 15, Fragments of Giovanni Metaxà
(Election by *consigliere et vice gerente* Marin Boldù, 30 March 1712)

[1716]

<i>Vathy</i>	<i>Anogi</i>	<i>Exogi</i>
Giorgo Dendrinò	Demetro Paisi	Francesco
quondam Thomà	quondam Papà	Maurocheffallo
Costantin	Costantin Maruda	Allexandro Vrettò
Vlassopullo quondam	Ventura Moraiti	quondam Zagni
Manolli		

⁷⁴ The names of the existing *sindici* for Vathy are given in the preamble to the election, noting that they are re-elected for another term: ‘a removazione anco de sconcerti, e scandali Hà terminato che li Sindici Attuali, che come Giorgio Petala di Janni, e Francesco Solomon habbino a continuare a tal’ incarico risservando la decisio[ne] delle loro differenze alla Carica suprema di Sua Eccellenza Proveditor Generall con Autorità di Capitan Generall’.

⁷⁵ The folio is very water-damaged.

Niccoletto Marulli
quondam Thomà

ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, vol. M. Colonia (1716), ff. 559v–561v
(Election by *consiglier et vice gerente* Francesco Dandolo, 31 March 1716)

[1722]

<i>Vathy</i>	<i>Anogi</i>	<i>Exogi</i>
Dottor Francesco Salomon	Constantin Paisi quondam Pappà	Cristoforo Prossalendi
Dottor Stathi Petala Savò quondam Anastasio	Stathi Calinico Andrea Maruda quondam Janni	Antonio Vretò tis Petalùs ⁷⁶
Dottor Constantin Dendrinò quondam Giorgo		

ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, vol. G. Dalladecima (1721–2), ff. 111r–113v
(Election by *consiglier et vice gerente* Anzolo Foscarini, 31 March 1722)

[1753]

<i>Vathy</i>	<i>Anogi</i>	<i>Exogi</i>
Dottor Todorin Vlassopulo quondam Zorzi	Dottor Zaneto Galati Dottor Menego Paisi quondam Demetrio	Dottor Giorgio Vretto quondam Stamatelo [Dottor Metaxà Vreto di Papà] ⁷⁷
Dottor Todorin Dendrinò Draculi		Dottor Nicoletto Vretto Nuzato

⁷⁶ Matronymic, i.e. τῆς Πεταλοῦς.

⁷⁷ The name of Metaxà Vreto di Papà is struck out with an addendum signed by the *consiglier et vice gerente* Andrea Venier noting that his election was opposed for being a ‘persona incapace e de malla vità’, replacing him with Nicoletto Vretto Nuzato.

Dottor Demetrio
Maruli quondam
Giorgo

ΓAK–TI, ABΔ, vol. M. Metaxà (1753), *Libro Io straordinario*, ff. 112r–113v
(Election by *consigliere et vice gerente* Andrea Venier, 31 March 1753)

[1757]

<i>Vathy</i>	<i>Anogi</i>	<i>Exogi</i>
Dottor Demetrio Petalà Savò	Dottor Zaneto Galati	-

Dottor Costantin
Draculi Dendrinò

ΓAK–TI, ABΔ, vol. M. Focà (1757–58), *Libro straordinario*, ff. 51r–52r
(Election by *consigliere et vice gerente* Andrea Balbi, 31 March 1757)
The officeholders of Exogi are not included.

[1761]

<i>Vathy</i>	<i>Anogi</i>	<i>Exogi</i>
Dottor Demetrio Dendrinò Draculi quondam Giacomo	Dottor Zaneto Gallati Dottor Menego Paisi ⁷⁸	Dottor Demetrio Vretto Dottor Giorgio Vretto
Dottor Costantin Pettala Savò quondam Nicolò		Tarifa quondam Stamatelo
Dottor Gerasimo Caravia quondam Christodulo		

ΓAK–TI, ABΔ, vol. G. Cambici (1761–2), ff. 217v–219v
(Election by *consigliere et vice gerente* Barbarigo Da Riva, 31 March 1761)

⁷⁸ Beside his name is added ‘Confermato’.

[1763]

<i>Vathy</i>	<i>Anogi</i>	<i>Exogi</i>
Dottor Demetrio Solomon quondam Francesco	Dottor Zanetto Galatti quondam Zorzi	Dottor Giorgio Vrettò quondam Stamattello Dottor Attanasio
Dottor Zorzi Dendrinó di Costantin	Dottor Giorgio Paisi quondam Costantin	Prossalendi quondam Gerolamo
Dottor Costantin Pettalà Savò quondam Niccolò		

ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, vol. V. Metaxà (1763–4, i), ff. 46r–47v
(Election by *consiglier et vice gerente* Gerolamo Maria Soranzo,
31 March 1763)

[1765]

<i>Vathy</i>	<i>Anogi</i>	<i>Exogi</i>
-	Dottor Menego Paisi	Dottor Costantin Vrettò quondam Demetrio

ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, «Σπαράγματα», Box 17, Unattributable fragment.
(Election by *consiglier et vice gerente* Pietro Girolamo Barbaro, [31 March]
1765; the earlier folios are lost, including the election of Vathy)

[1771]

<i>Vathy</i>	<i>Anogi</i>	<i>Exogi</i>
Dottor Gerasimo Caravià quondam Cristodulo	Dottor Gregorio Galati Dottor Caruso	Dottor Antonio Lecazza Dottor Anzolin
Dottor Tomà Dendrino	Maruda	Vrettò quondam Demetrio

Dottor Panagin
Vlassopulo quondam
Nicolin

ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, vol. G. Anino (1770–1, ii), *Libro Proclami et Extraordinario*,
ff.nn. (Election by *consigliere et vice gerente* Gerolamo Antonio Dandolo,
31 March 1771)

[1773]

<i>Vathy</i>	<i>Anogi</i>	<i>Exogi</i>
Demetrio Draculi	Cristodulo Paxinò	Giorgo Vrettò
Costantin Savò quondam Nicolò	Nicolin Gallati	Nuzzato Giorgo Vrettò Graciato

ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, vol. P. Schiadan (1773, ii), *Lettere*, cc.nn.
(Election by *consigliere et vice gerente* Andrea Bòn, 30 March 1773)

[1775]

<i>Vathy</i>	<i>Anogi</i>	<i>Exogi</i>
Alvise Savò quondam Stati	Stamati Paisi Demetrio Galati	Anzolo Vretò quondam Demetrio Giorgo Vretò Tarifa
Janni Vlasopulo Todorin Stati Dendrinò Todorin		

ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, «Σπαράγματα», Box 17, Unattributable fragment.
(Election by *consigliere et vice gerente* Daniel Balbi, 30 March 1775)

[1776]

<i>Vathy</i>	<i>Anogi</i>	<i>Exogi</i>
Stati Draculi quondam Todorin	Demetrio Gallati quondam Nicolin	Giorgo Vretò quondam Stamattello

Janni Vlassopulo quondam Todorin	Stamati Paisi quondam Marchin	Anzolin Vretò quondam Demetrio
Alvise Savò quondam Stati		

ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, vol. V. Dalladecima (1776–7), cc.nn.
(List of ‘Sindici e Primati’, 6 February 1776)

[1777]

<i>Vathy</i>	<i>Anogi</i>	<i>Exogi</i>
Dottor Stati	Dottor Metaxà Paisi	Dottor Giorgio Vrettò
Dendrinò Draculi Teodoro	quondam Costantin	Tariffa
Dottor Zuanne	Dottor Cristodulo	Dottor Attanasio
Vlassopulo quondam Todorin	Gallati quondam Zaneto	Prossalendi
Dottor Alvise Savò Pettalà quondam Eustachio		

ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, vol. V. Dalladecima (1776–7), *Lettere*, cc.nn.
(Election by *consigliere et vice gerente* Alvise Antonio Zorzi, 31 March 1777)

[1779]

<i>Vathy</i>	<i>Anogi</i>	<i>Exogi</i>
Dottor Costantin	Dottor Domenico	Dottor Giorgio Vrettò
Draculi Dendrinò quondam Demetrio	Paisi quondam Demetrio	Muzzato ⁷⁹
Dottor Costantin	Dottor Gregorio	Dottor Nicolin
Savò quondam Nicolò	Galati quondam Vicco	Vrettò quondam Costantin

ΓΑΚ–ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, «Σπαράγματα», Box 17, Unattributable fragment.
(Election by *consigliere et vice gerente* Christofolo Bonlini, 30 March 1779)

⁷⁹ Read *Nuzzato*.

[1782]

<i>Vathy</i>	<i>Anogi</i>	<i>Exogi</i>
Dottor Marin Savò quondam Nicolin	Dottor Cristodulo Paxinò quondam Pietro	Dottor Nicolin Vrettò quondam Zuanne
Dottor Statti Dendrinò Draculi quondam Teodoro		

ΓΑΚ-ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, «Σπαράγματα», Box 37, Fragments of Spiridion Loverdo, *Libro straordinario*, f. 5r. (Election by *governator e capitano* Spiridion Loverdo, 18 January 1782)

[1784]

<i>Vathy</i>	<i>Anogi</i>	<i>Exogi</i>
Dottore Spiridion Draculi quondam Signor Janni	Dottore Menego Paisi quondam Signor Demetrio	Dottore Nicolin Vrettò quondam Signor Costantin
Dottore Costantin Savo quondam Signor Vettor		

ΓΑΚ-ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, «Σπαράγματα», Box 18, Fragments of Zuanne Anino, [ff. 144r-v]. (Election by *governator e capitano* Zuanne Anino, 29 February 1784)

[1787]

<i>Vathy</i>	<i>Anogi</i>	<i>Exogi</i>
Li Clarissimi Dottori Costantin Caravia di Alessandro	Il Clarissimo Dottor Zuanne Paisi quondam Anastasio	Il Clarissimo Stati Nuzzato di Papà Zani
Dottor Costantin Draculi		

ΓΑΚ-ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, «Σπαράγματα», Box 24, Fragments of Theodoro Assani, [*Libro straordinario?*], [ff. 7r-v (Vathy), 9r-v (Anogi), 14r-v (Exogi)] (Election by *governator e capitano* Theodoro Assani, in separate documents of 22 and 25 January, 12 February 1787)

[1796]

<i>Vathy</i>	<i>Anogi</i>	<i>Exogi</i>
Dottor Michiel Roditi	Dottor Giorgo	Dottor Cristodulo
Dottor Zorzi	Galati	Vrettò
Vlassopulo		

ΓΑΚ-ΤΙ, ΑΒΔ, «Σπαράγματα», Box 30, Fragments of Gerasimo Policalà, [*Filze lettere*], f. 41. (Mentioned in a letter of the *provveditor* of Cephalonia Giacomo Marin, 15 May 1797). The towns from which the *sindici* were elected are not stated, but are clear on the basis of name patterns.

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Abstract

This article attempts a reconstruction of the system of local government in Ithaca during three centuries of Venetian rule (1500–1797), based on unpublished documents from the state archives of the island. While the island's governor was sent from Cephalonia, several offices of the local administration were filled by Ithacesians who were appointed each year by the Venetians. These officeholders undertook daily bureaucratic functions, maintained the public order, oversaw the ports to protect from seaborne disease, and kept watch of the coasts. The highest of these officers, the handful of *sindici* elected from the three main towns Vathy, Anogi and Exogi, were invariably prominent figures in the island's society. The documents allow us to trace ongoing tensions between the Ithacesians,

their Cephalonian governor, and the higher Venetian administrators over the right of government in Ithaca. Between the sixteenth and eighteenth centuries the Ithacesians made several petitions for the increase of local participation, leading to several reforms expanding the involvement of Ithacesians and culminating with the establishment of a deliberative body on the island in the last years of Venetian rule. The article is accompanied by a list names of *sindici* from 1649 to 1796, which reveals the dominance of the three towns by a small number of powerful clans.

Περίληψη

Οι «προεστοί» της βενετικής Ιθάκης: ένα σκιαγράφημα της τοπικής διοίκησης μαζί με έναν κατάλογο των συνδίκων (1649–1796)

Το παρόν άρθρο επιχειρεί μια αναπαράσταση του συστήματος τοπικής διοίκησης στην Ιθάκη κατά την διάρκεια τριών αιώνων βενετικής κυριαρχίας (1500–1797), βάσει ανέκδοτων εγγράφων από τα κρατικά αρχεία του νησιού. Ενώ ο κυβερνήτης του νησιού ερχόταν από την Κεφαλονιά, πολλά αξιώματα της τοπικής διοίκησης τα κατείχαν Ιθακήσιοι που διορίζονταν κάθε χρόνο από τους Βενετούς. Αυτοί οι αξιωματούχοι αναλάμβαναν καθημερινά γραφειοκρατικά καθήκοντα, διατηρούσαν την δημόσια τάξη, επέβλεπαν τα λιμάνια για την προστασία από τις ασθένειες της θάλασσας και επιτηρούσαν τις ακτές. Οι ανώτεροι από αυτούς τους αξιωματούχους, η ολιγάριθμη ομάδα των συνδίκων (*sindici*) που εκλέγονταν από τα τρία κύρια χωριά Βαθύ, Ανωγή και Εξωγή, ήταν πάντοτε επιφανείς προσωπικότητες της κοινωνίας του νησιού. Τα έγγραφα μας επιτρέπουν να εντοπίσουμε τις συνεχιζόμενες εντάσεις μεταξύ των Ιθακησίων, του κεφαλονίτη κυβερνήτη τους και των ανώτερων βενετών αξιωματούχων σχετικά με το δικαίωμα της διακυβέρνησης της Ιθάκης. Μεταξύ του δέκατου έκτου και του δέκατου όγδοου αιώνα οι Ιθακήσιοι υπέβαλαν αρκετές αιτήσεις για την αύξηση της συμμετοχής του τοπικού πληθυσμού, οι οποίες οδήγησαν σε διάφορες μεταρρυθμίσεις που διέυρναν την συμμετοχή των Ιθακησίων και κορυφώθηκαν με την σύσταση ενός διαβουλευτικού σώματος στο νησί κατά τα τελευταία χρόνια της βενετικής κυριαρχίας. Το άρθρο συνοδεύεται από έναν κατάλογο ονομάτων των συνδίκων από το 1649 έως το 1796, ο οποίος φανερώνει την κυριαρχία των τριών χωριών από έναν μικρό αριθμό ισχυρών οικογενειών.